

RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN ETHICAL LEADERSHIP PRACTICES, POSITIVE SCHOOL CLIMATE AND TRUST IN LEADERS IN PUBLIC SCHOOLS OF LAHORE

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Abstract

Integrating values into school management is critical for balancing school administrator's roles as both leaders and administrators. The aim of present research was to explore association amongst ethical headship practices, positive school climate and trust in leaders as alleged by the public-school teachers of Lahore. The present study employed a correlational research design and data were gathered using ethical leadership at workplace, trust in leader and organizational climate description questionnaire questionnaires. 150 female respondents were selected from the 14 public schools of Lahore, by using convenience sampling technique. The correlation among the three parameters: Ethical leadership practices by the principals, positive school climate and trust in leaders was computed through spearman's rank difference correlation and pearson's product moment correlation. The findings of the present study revealed a highly significant correlation among all three parameters for teachers at primary level. However, in comparison to the primary and high school levels, no significant relation was reported between ethical leadership practices and positive school climate at the middle level. Instead, a significant relationship was observed between ethical headship practices and trust in leaders as perceived by the middle school teachers. Furthermore, at the high school level, the findings showed a highly significant relationship amongst ethical headship practices and trust in leaders as perceived by the teachers at high school level whereas significant relationship was found between ethical leadership practices and positive school climate. Therefore, significant relationships were determined among all the three parameters except for ethical leadership practices and positive school climate at middle school. The findings revealed statistically significant differences in perceptions of ethical leadership, positive school climate and trust in leadership across three

groups of schools i.e elementary, middle and high school. The results of this study propose that ethical management performs are of foremost importance for generating a positive school learning environment and fostering trust in leaders among teachers.

Keywords: Leader's Ethical Practices, Positive School Climate, Trust in Leaders.

INTRODUCTION

Every member belonging to any organisation or officialdom must be trained and educated to undertake the concern of taking verdicts since headship excellence is even looked-for by others farther down the line to accomplish the duties at their levels (Demir, Budur, Hiwa, & Heshmati, 2021). These basic leadership skills are the needful of this today's modern era. Positive school climate and trust are the prerequisites of a successful educational organizations and this question is of great importance that on which factors these two essential aspects depend upon. According to recent studies, knowledge management facilitators have a positive direct and indirect impact on the knowledge management process (Iqbal, 2021; Yadav, Pant & Seth, 2020). In the modern world, organizations undoubtedly work hard to improve the performance of their employees. Since trust fosters a culture of mutual respect and value among coworkers and innovators, it also increases employee loyalty and engagement (O'Dwyer et al., 2023). Corporate indiscretion, malfeasance, and corruption have received a lot of media attention lately. For example, in 2016, Wells Fargo slid from a position of high respectability to being characterized as one of the most disliked American firms owing to the discovery of unethical business practices (Gujarathi & Barua, 2017; Stebbins & Comen, 2017). There is emerging evidence that, in addition to employee personal traits, cues in the corporate environment play a major influence in deciding unethical behavior (Kish-Gephart, Harrison, & Treviño, 2010; Martin & Cullen, 2006; Newman, Round, Bhattacharya, & Roy, 2017).

Organizations greatly value the role; ethics play in leadership courses. Past examinations likewise showed that heads of the school had connections with scholarly accomplishment/successes either directly or in an unintended scheme (Ibrahim, Ghavifekr, Ling, Siraj, & Azeez, (2014). It had been proven in previous studies that responsibility of mentors towards the undertakings shared with them start with the solace and satisfaction in their work. Every one of their activities are inferable that make the presence of an air and work climate in schools laborious and remembering the way to deal with authority for school executives (Abdul Wahab, Mohd Fuad, Ismail & Majid 2014). Employees may effectively use resources and put in their best efforts in an environment that is created by a culture that is transparent and fosters constructive collaboration. Moreover, it cultivates a feeling of inclusion and dedication that enhances output and effectiveness (Azeem et al., 2021; Schmiedel et al., 2019). Additionally, the supportive culture fosters adaptable actions and ongoing learning, which better prepares staff members to respond appropriately and complete their jobs. This may eventually result in the efficacy of the organization (Chatman & O'Reilly, 2016). Culture is essential for encouraging cooperation and teamwork (Xiong et al., 2021). The more honest and fairer the leadership would be the better would be the staff members' performance. As Pakistan

is a developing country, we have a lot of serious issues regarding our educational system at the level of leadership such as favouritism, inequity among the distribution of duties, unfair usage of power and position, refusal from the teachers' educational and professional capabilities and their humiliation. We have to be very honest and fair at all levels of our system. Recent study had revealed significant differences in how staff workers perceive climate, with some reporting far more favourable involvements than others (Capp, Astor, & Gilreath, 2020).

In the twenty-first century, when humans are driven by technology, it's time for school leaders to benefit from value-based leadership styles that put an emphasis on ethical practises because technology-driven cultures tend to disregard the value of ethics in the workplace. Based on the needs that are now being met worldwide, leadership styles, practises, and theories are all deemed to be equally effective. The finest school leadership techniques can be greatly influenced by a diversity of aspects, comprising school necessities, teacher requirements, creative practises, student enactment, national enterprises, legislative variations, educational advancements, and complications encountered in schools (Amanchukwu, Stanly, & Olorube, 2015; Park, 2012, Jibril Qaralleh, 2021). In twenty-first century, experienced and novice principals' leadership practices appear to be adopting various paths, behavioural viewpoints, and representations in managing an association (Bush, 2007; Ahmad Mukhtar & Chan, 2020). A strong, supportive culture fosters cooperation and respect amongst coworkers as well as a supportive culture and the dissemination of important task-related information, all of which can improve employee and organizational effectiveness (Njagi et al., 2020). It's vital and even significant for school influential to be responsive for these potential sources of variance and take steps to address any disparities in the excellence of the school environment encountered by different groups of work force. This can involve providing targeted support and resources to specific groups, as well as working to create a more positive and inclusive overall school culture (Capp, Astor, & Gilreath, 2020).

Statement of the Problem

The issue that present study tried to address was the dearth of precise evaluation standards for ethical leadership practises by school principals in Lahore's public schools, which may have an effect on the educational environment and academic growth of children. From the viewpoint of teachers of public schools at Lahore, the major aim of this research was to study the association amongst moral headship behaviour, a supportive learning environment, and trust in school leadership. The ethical standards of school leaders in our country should be assessed because they have a weighty effect on the schooling milieu and, ultimately, the academic progress of students. This is true even though there is no proof that the best policies or training are only available to school principals. Assessing the ethical standards of school leaders is crucial to ensure that they are creating a non-toxic and encouraging learning milieu for their students. However, assessing these standards can be challenging, as ethical behaviour can be subjective and difficult to quantify. While there is no proof that the best policies or training are only available to school principals, it is essential to provide on-going training and support for

all school leaders to ensure they are upholding ethical standards and creating a positive learning environment. Ultimately, assessing the ethical standards of school leaders is important for ensuring that students have the best possible learning environment. By upholding ethical standards, school influential can generate values that support academic achievement and prepare students for success in the future.

Purpose of the Study

A key objective behind this study was to find out relation amongst ethical leadership practises, a positive learning environment, and teacher's trust in leadership. If there exists a relation between leaders' ethical behaviours and constructive school atmosphere, this data could be used to identify effective leadership practices capable of bringing about the desired changes in the current school environment. The study's aim was to gather teachers' perspectives on the efficacy of leaders' ethical management behaviours and constructive atmosphere practises, which had not previously been investigated in Pakistan's context. In this study, the researcher wanted to know what factors were related with a positive school climate and trust in leadership in order to raise educational standards for students. The study also made useful recommendations for creating a positive learning environment in schools and promoting trust in educational institutions.

Objectives

This research had specific goals and objectives, including:

1. To determine the relationship between school principals' ethical leadership practices and a positive school climate as perceived by the public-school teachers of Lahore at primary level.
2. To explore the relationship between school principals' ethical leadership practices and a positive school climate as perceived by the public-school teachers of Lahore at middle level.
3. To find out the relationship between school principals' ethical leadership practices and a positive school climate as perceived by the public-school teachers of Lahore at secondary level.
4. To investigate the relationship between ethical leadership practices and trust in their leaders as perceived by the public-school teachers of Lahore at primary level.
5. To determine the relationship between ethical leadership practices and trust in their leaders as perceived by the public-school teachers of Lahore at middle level.
6. To examine the relationship between ethical leadership practices and trust in their leaders as perceived by the public-school teachers of Lahore at secondary level.

Hypotheses

- H_a:** There is a significant correlation between ethical leadership practices and positive school climate as perceived by the primary public-school teachers of Lahore.
- H_a:** There is a significant correlation between ethical leadership practices and positive school climate as perceived by the middle public-school teachers of Lahore.
- H_a:** There is a significant correlation between ethical leadership practices and positive school climate as perceived by the secondary public-school teachers of Lahore.
- H_a:** There is a significant correlation between ethical leadership practices and trust in leader as perceived by the primary public-school teachers of Lahore.
- H_a:** There is a significant correlation between ethical leadership practices and trust in leader as perceived by the middle public-school teachers of Lahore.
- H_a:** There is a significant correlation between ethical leadership practices and trust in leader as perceived by the secondary public-school teachers of Lahore.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Leadership is a complicated, multifaceted phenomenon (DePree, 1989). Leadership focuses on inspiring and motivating others (Kotter, 1990). In Brown's 2005 definition of ethical leadership, is the spearhead's responsibility as a "moral manager" and "moral person" is made apparent, along with the capacity to equalize the responsibilities of a manager and an active figurehead in the workplace. The group leader is responsible for upholding the principles and norms they have established. "Ethical leadership" refers to a head that supports noble values, doctrines, and upright behaviours in their speech, behaviour, actions, and making choices; as a result, he or she is able to encourage followers to uphold comparable moral standards in their pursuit of a common objective (Brown, M. E., & Trevino, L. K. 2006). Trust is a prerequisite for effective leadership and decision-making in an organization. Employees are more inclined to support the mission and core values of the company when they have faith in its leaders (Tan & Md. Noor, 2013). People are more willing to accept responsibility for their responsibilities when there is widespread trust, which boosts output and performance and increases organizational effectiveness (Dębski et al., 2020).

Leadership and Management (Difference)

Although not being the same thing, management and leadership go hand in glove. Leadership and management both involve a specific set of duties or obligations. Although there are some similarities between managers and leaders in that they both practice exceptional capabilities to convince people to achieve particular aims, there are some glaring variances too (Northouse, 2007). As the study of management dates from the turn of the 20th century and our modern society, the leadership field has its roots in Aristotle's principles. Planning, organising, staffing, and controlling were the four main key processes as initially defined by Fayol (1916), and they remain indicative of management today (Northouse 2013, 12). Even without a formal position or power, anyone can

exercise good leadership. Effective leadership does not require a lot of experience, a high-profile position, a big team, or board-level authority. Leaders assess the present position and boost new characters, managers focus on keeping a well-functioning office and search for long-term objectives (Yukl, 1989).

Effective leaders, on the other hand, are those who carry out plans and bring about change. Relationships and the capacity to influence are what determine leadership more than hierarchical rank. Motivate, produce, and grow individuals (including the leader himself). Leadership entails responsibility first and foremost: whoever assumes a prominent place and more concern for the sake of welfare of people/families too. Many managers who hold the highest positions in organizations or government agencies are not leaders. Workforce has to abide by their orders because they have influence over the subordinates. Contrarily, many individuals who do not have official leadership positions have made the decision to value and respect their co-workers and the subordinates are compelled to pursue them everywhere (Sinek, 2011).

Role of Ethics in Educational Institutes

Starratt (2004) defines morals as "a specific education about guiding ideas, norms, and attitudes that sustain moral behaviour". This point of view broadens the concept of integrity to embrace a more wide-ranging view of human life. The holistic nature and meaning of ethics set it apart from morality. Ethics is somewhat more complete term than morals and ethics. In line, morality is defined as "the substitute from out principled commitments and beliefs" (Starratt, 2004). Morals/Ethics are the units of ethics that is focused on actions and conduct.

The contributions of employees cannot be reduced to a superficial appearance of reciprocity. This demonstrates that employees do not receive compensation that is fair to their contributions to helping the company turn a profit and increase turnover edge for such businesses. Workforces are a company's most valued strength as they steer the company's direction and play a significant role in determining whether it succeeds or fails; they are the organization's public face. They frequently join the firm with the strength of their appropriate expertise, abilities, and experiences; they are the company's initial clients; they are the ones who support the company; and a bigger percentage of employees give their all to advance the company (Hobson, 2019). To facilitate the firm in achieving its goals, employees execute a variety of duties and exert tremendous effort.

Motivated workers, in particular, routinely surpass goals, satisfy customers' requirements and requests (and sometimes even go above and beyond them), and even create new, cutting-edge products (or improve on already-existing ones for the organization's advantage). Thus, an ethical leader can instil the true spirit of motivations among the staff members by the ethical behaviours in the organization. That very leader should give the employees the space for achieving the organization's goals.

Theoretical Framework

Traditionally, it has made sense from an empirical perspective to support investigations with pertinent theories that could expand on the meaning of the concepts being examined. The theory of the leader-member exchange (LXM) serves as the foundation for this study.

Leader-member exchange theory (LXM)

The LMX theory asserts that the quality in the workgroup was favourably correlated with the leader's discretion. High personal wisdom in leaders encourages followers to pursue moral lifestyles that are good both for themselves and others as well (Ardelt 2004; Baltes & Staudinger 2000). It is essential that intelligent leaders and their followers have a higher calibre of relationship than less intelligent commanders and their followers. People who are wise have developed and well-rounded personalities, excellent decision-making abilities in light of difficult life circumstances, and a compassionate and empathic approach to others (Ardelt 2004). High-compassionate leaders foster a positive atmosphere in subordinates' mind and hearts (Cosley, McCoy, Saslow & Epel, 2010). This activity shows followers that the company values them, which in turn lessens the poor self-evaluation that comes from feeling isolated at work. Because a crucial psychological mechanism connecting high loneliness to poor LMX is adverse self-evaluation (Chen, Langner, & Mendoza-Denton, 2009).

Love from a leader can counteract the effects of loneliness. Additionally, when subordinates experience strong sympathy from their superiors, they will believe that these people are trustworthy and deserving of their respect. This idea that teacher self-efficacy increases in settings where LMX is present is supported by studies by Basu and Graen (1997) and Deluga (1998). This results in a more comprehensively committed workforce, which in turn strengthens Organizational Citizenship Behaviour (OCB), which "deals with the acts and behaviours that are not needed by workers."

They do not directly add to the assignment at hand, but they are advantageous to the team and promote even more effective organizational functioning (Status Net, 2019). We can draw the conclusion that LMX quality is favourably correlated with a leader's wisdom. Ethical leaders enforce and encourage being ethical to their subordinates in addition to setting a good example for others by their ideas, words, and deeds.

The Trait approach (LMX THEORY) is a relational theory that places an emphasis on the connections and values represented by leaders and followers (Bligh 2017). By reviewing several studies on leadership and trust, the LMX theory was connected to trust, claiming that employees have better connections with trusted managers compared to untrusted managers. Contrarily, it was assumed that a head's trust was essential for judging an individual's good job engagement.

Conceptual Framework

Figure: Ethical Leadership Practices, Positive School Climate, and Trust in Leaders as Perceived by the Teachers in Public Schools of Lahore

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Research Paradigm

The paradigm for this research is as follow:

The positivism philosophy is rooted in a robust empirical foundation. Since this is a quantitative study, it is underpinned by the positivistic research paradigm (Yoon, Konge, Lars &Anthony, 2019). Positivism aligns with the hypothetical-deductive model of science, which leverages experimental data and an underlying hypothesis to operationalize variables and measures. The results of hypothesis testing are then applied to advance the field of knowledge. As a key goal of positivist paradigm is to discover associations or correlations that can predict or control the phenomenon being studied (Sciarra ,1999, Gergen,2001) therefore, for this purpose this paradigm will provide a clear lens to understand the findings of this study.

Quantitative Research Approach

In the process of quantifying data and statistically examine it in order to accept or deny "alternative knowledge propositions," quantitative research involves the collecting of data. (Creswell, 2003).

The research design for the present study is given below:

Study Design

It was a correlational study design. A sample of 150 female participants from 14 public schools of Lahore was chosen by using convenience sampling technique. A questionnaire tool was designed to estimate about teachers' observations of their principal's ethical headship behaviours, the school's culture, and their level of trust in leaders, was administered to study participants. To collect the quantitative data for this study, three

scales were used: The Ethical Leadership Scale (ELS), the Trust in Leaders Scale and Organizational climate description questionnaire (OCDQ-REVISED). The ELS, created by Yilmaz in 2006, was used to evaluate the ethical behaviour of principals in schools and other educational institutions whereas the scale TLS was developed by Adams and Sartori in 2005. The OCDQ has been updated three times since its creation by Hoy and Clover in 1986 to create versions tailored for elementary, middle, and high school levels. After the collection of data, correlation was calculated on SPSS by using Pearson Product Moment Correlation and Spearman's Rank Difference Correlation.

Research Tool

The research tool (close ended questionnaire) for this study was as follow:

Questionnaire

To gather quantitative data for this study, two scales were used: The Ethical Leadership Scale (ELS) and the Trust in Leaders Scale (TLS). The ELS, created by Yilmaz in 2006, was used to evaluate the ethical behaviour of principals in schools and other educational institutions. Participants were requested to express their level of acceptance with proclamations on a scale of 1-5, 1 showing absolute disagreement and 5 demonstrating complete agreement. The Organizational Climate Descriptive Questionnaire (OCDQ) was also used to metre the atmosphere in educational institutes (schools). The OCDQ has been updated three times since its creation by Hoy and Clover in 1986 to create versions tailored for elementary, middle, and high school levels. The OCDQ-REVISED was used in this study to evaluate instructors' at all three levels. Respondents were requested to answer on a four-point scale ranging from "very rarely" to "often occurs. The Trust in Leaders Scale (TLS), created by Adams and Sartori in 2005, was used to measure the level of trust perceived by Lahore public school teachers. Respondents were asked to score their level of agreement with different statements on a seven-point scale, with 1 indicating complete agreement and 5 indicating complete disagreement.

In addition to these scales, the questionnaire also included questions about demographic information, such as respondents' experience and education. All personal information about participants kept confidential. Respondents were asked to complete the questionnaire by marking the appropriate answer or providing the best choice. Closed ended questions were used, with all possible answers listed and respondents selecting the most appropriate category according to their personal opinion.

Population

The population of the present research study consisted on the female educators working at Lahore's public schools. 14 public schools from Lahore district participated in this study. The population is generally represented by the alphabet capital letter N (Krieger, 2012).

Sample Size

The convenience sampling which is non-probability sampling technique was utilized for collection of data from the respondents. 150 female respondents were selected as study

sample from 14 public schools of Lahore, Pakistan (to whom a closed ended questionnaire was administered).

Sampling Strategy

Sampling strategy can be defined as the way the researcher choice folks, students or electors for data collection is called the sampling strategy or sampling design (Kumar, 2011).

Data Collection Procedure

The questionnaire was administered to 150 teachers of public schools of Lahore, Pakistan. The motive of the research was made clear to the respondents, furthermore, if the respondents of the study would find any questions about the nature of the study the researchers would respond to their queries briefly to satisfy the respondents.

Data Analysis Techniques

For the purpose to discover the relationship amongst the variables under investigation in present study, statistical software called SPSS (Statistical Package for Social Sciences) was used. The data was analysed using two kinds of correlation tests, named as Pearson Product Moment Correlation and Spearman's Rank Difference Correlation. The Pearson correlation test was used to measure the strength of a linear relationship amongst two continuous variables. It produces a correlation coefficient ranging from -1 to +1, where a positive value shows a positive correlation and a negative value shows a negative correlation.

The strength of the correlation is determined by the magnitude of the coefficient, with values nearer to +1 or -1 indicating a stronger relationship. The Spearman rank correlation, on the other hand, was utilized to quantify the strength of a relationship amongst two variables that may not have a linear relationship. It produces a correlation coefficient grounded on the ranks of the data, than on the actual values. The coefficient ranges from -1 to +1, where a positive value indicates a positive correlation and a negative value indicates a negative correlation. Again, the strength of the correlation is determined by the magnitude of the coefficient. By conducting both Pearson's product moment correlation and Spearman's rank difference coefficient correlation, the researcher was able to attain a more complete understanding of the relationships between the variables in this study. This information can be used to draw meaningful conclusions and make informed decisions based on the results.

Table 1: Correlation Coefficient

Sr. No.	Interval coefficient	Level of correlation
1	0.20 - 0.35	Weak
2	0.35 -0.65	Moderate
3	0.65 – 0.85	Strong
4	Over 0.85	Very strong

Source: Cohen. L, Manion, L &Morrison, K, (2007, p.536).

DATA ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

The survey questionnaire administered to each participant included questions asking for certain demographic information such as their education and experience. Question no. 1 and 2 of the survey questionnaires was based on demographic information. Only female participants (teachers of primary, middle and high schools) responded for the present research.

In this study the validity and reliability were also verified by the experts, so that the results would be more reliable. The population was comprised of the female teachers of 14 public schools of Lahore district in Pakistan. The sample size comprised of 150 respondents after eliminating the outliers from the survey who hadn't completed or not responded seriously (incomplete response) to the questionnaire of the research.

Table 2: Demographic Information

Sr. No.	Institute	Level	No. of respondents	Gender
1	Public	Primary/elementary	50	Female
2	Public	Middle	50	Female
3	Public	High	50	Female

Table 2 depicts total 150 Number of participants participated in the study, 50 from each level of school i.e. primary, middle and high public schools of Lahore district.

Results of Data at Primary Level

Table 4: Qualification of the Respondents

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Bachelor	4	8.0	8.0	8.0
	Master	16	32.0	32.0	40.0
	MPhil	30	60.0	60.0	100.0
	Total	50	100.0	100.0	

Table 4 depicts the qualification of the study defendants. A total number of 50 participants from the primary level participated in the study. Out of 50 there were 4(8%), respondents who held bachelor's degree, 16(32%) participants had done their masters while 30 (60%) participants had completed their MPhil.

Table 5: Experience of Respondent

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	1-10years	24	48.0	48.0	48.0
	11-20years	20	40.0	40.0	88.0
	21 and more	6	12.0	12.0	100.0
	Total	50	100.0	100.0	

Table 5 represents the experience of the study defendants. 24 (48%) respondents had an experience of 1-10 years, 20(40%) respondents had 11-20 years' experience whereas 6 (12%) respondents had an experience of 21 or more than 21 years' experience.

Table 6: Correlation between Ethical Leadership Practices, Positive School Climate in Leaders as perceived by public school teachers at Primary Level

		ELP_Scores	PSC_Scores
ELP_Scores	Pearson Correlation	1	.528**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	50	50
PSC_Scores	Pearson Correlation	.528**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	50	50

* $p < .05$ * ELP: Ethical Leadership Practices; *PSC: Positive School Climate

Table 6 shows that ethical leadership practices observed a strong positive correlation ($r=0.528$) with the positive school climate as perceived by the public-school teachers of Lahore at primary level.

Correlation was calculated using Pearson's Product Moment correlation on SPSS as the data was normally distributed. This degree of association demonstrates that only a leadership style that is impartial and fair can create a positive learning environment in schools.

The p value is 0.000 which is less than 0.05 which shows that there is a highly significant relationship among ELP and PSC. Therefore, null hypothesis is overruled, and alternate hypothesis is recognized.

Table 7: Correlation between Ethical Leadership Practices and Trust in Leaders as perceived by public school teachers at Primary Level at Primary Level

		ELP_Scores	TL_Scores
ELP_Scores	Pearson Correlation	1	.804**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	50	50
TL_Scores	Pearson Correlation	.804**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	50	50

* $p < .05$ * ELP: Ethical Leadership Practices; *TL: Trust in Leaders

Table 7 shows a strong positive correlation among ethical leadership practices and trust in leaders as observed by the public-school teachers of Lahore at primary level. Correlation was calculated by using Pearson's Product Moment correlation on SPSS as the data was normally distributed.

The p value is 0.000 which is less than 0.05 which shows that there is a highly significant relationship between ELP and TL. Therefore, the null hypothesis is not accepted and alternate hypothesis is accepted. This degree of association suggests that the only way to increase people's faith in leaders is to act impartially and justly.

Results of Data at Middle Level

Table 8: Qualification of Respondent

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Bachelor	10	20.0	20.0	20.0
	Master	28	56.0	56.0	76.0
	M.Phil.	12	24.0	24.0	100.0
	Total	50	100.0	100.0	

Table 8 depicts the qualification of the study respondents. The sample comprised of 10(20%) participants with bachelor’s degree, 28(56%) participants had completed their masters whereas 12(24%) participants held MPhil degree. A total number of 50 participants from middle level participated in the study.

Table 9: Experience of Respondent

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	1-10years	17	34.0	34.0	34.0
	11-20years	17	34.0	34.0	68.0
	21 and more	16	32.0	32.0	100.0
	Total	50	100.0	100.0	

Table 9 shows the experience of the participants. 17 (34%) respondents had teaching experience of 1-10 years, 17(34%) respondents had 11-20 years of experience and 16 (32%) respondents had an experience of 21 or more than 21 years of teaching experience.

Table 10: Correlation between Ethical Leadership Practices, Positive School Climate as perceived by public school teachers at Middle Level

		ELP_Scores	PSC_Scores
ELP_Scores	Pearson Correlation	1	.150
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.297
	N	50	50
PSC_Scores	Pearson Correlation	.150	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.297	
	N	50	50

* $p < .05$ * ELP: Ethical Leadership Practices; *PSC: Positive School Climate

Table 10 illustrates that ethical leadership practices has a weak correlation ($r=0.150$) with the positive school climate as perceived by the public-school teachers of Lahore at middle level. Correlation was calculated by using Pearson’s Product Moment Correlation on SPSS as the data was normally distributed. The p value is 0.297 which is greater than 0.05 which shows that there is not a significant association between ELP and PSC. This degree of correlation demonstrates that the leaders must show impartial and unbiased attitude.

Table 11: Correlation between Ethical Leadership Practices and Trust in Leadership as perceived by public school teachers at Middle Level

		ELP_Scores	TL_Scores
ELP_Scores	Pearson Correlation	1	.798**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	50	50
TL_Scores	Pearson Correlation	.798**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	50	50

* $p < .05$ * ELP: Ethical Leadership Practices; *TL: Trust in Leaders

Table 11 shows that ethical leadership practices displayed a strong positive correlation ($r = 0.798$) with the trust in leaders as alleged by the public-school instructors of Lahore at middle level. Correlation was computed by using persons' product moment correlation on SPSS as the data was normally disseminated. Due to the strength of the link, it is clear that the leadership of the school is the only force that can foster a positive learning environment. The p value is 0.000 which is less than 0.05 which shows a highly significant relationship between ELP and TL. Therefore, the null hypothesis is precluded, and alternate hypothesis is recognized.

Results of Data at High Level

Table 12: Qualification of Respondent

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Bachelor	4	8.0	8.0	8.0
	Master	34	68.0	68.0	76.0
	MPhil	12	24.0	24.0	100.0
	Total	50	100.0	100.0	

Table 12 depicts the qualification of the study defendants. The sample comprised of 4 (8%) participants with bachelor's qualification, 34 (68%) participants had master's degree and 12 (24%) participants had completed their MPhil. A total number of 50 participants from high school participated in the study.

Table 13: Experience of Respondent

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	1-10years	16	32.0	32.0	32.0
	11-20years	22	44.0	44.0	76.0
	21 and more	12	24.0	24.0	100.0
	Total	50	100.0	100.0	

Table 13 shows the experience of the study participants. 16 (32%) respondents had teaching experience of 1-10 years, 22 (44%) respondents had 11-20 years of teaching experience while 12 (24%) respondents had teaching experience of 21 or more than 21 years.

Table 14: Correlation between Ethical Leadership Practices, Positive School Climates perceived by public school teachers at High School Level

			ELP_Scores	PSC_Scores
ELP_Scores	Spearman's rho	Rank Correlation	1.000	.398**
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.	.004
		N	50	50
PSC_Score	Spearman's rho	Rank Correlation	.398**	1.000
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.004	.
		N	50	50

* $p < .05$ * ELP: Ethical Leadership Practices; *PSC: Positive School Climate

Table 14 reveals that ethical leadership practices had a moderate positive correlation ($r=0.398$) with the positive school climate as perceived by the public-school teachers of Lahore at high school level in Pakistan. Correlation was calculated by using Spearman's rank difference correlation on SPSS as the data was not normally distributed. This degree of association demonstrates that the leadership must act impartially and equally to build a constructive learning milieu in the classroom. There must not be any favouritism among employees or the workforce. The p value is 0.004 which is less than 0.05 which shows that there is a significant association amongst ELP and PSC. Consequently, the null hypothesis is precluded and alternate hypothesis is acknowledged.

Table 15: Correlation between Ethical Leadership Practices and Trust in Leaders as perceived by public school teachers at High School Level

			ELP_Scores	TL_Scores
ELP_Scores	Spearman's rho	Correlation Coefficient	1.000	.659**
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.	.000
		N	50	50
TLScores	Spearman's rho	Correlation Coefficient	.659**	1.000
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.
		N	50	50

* $p < .05$ * ELP: Ethical Leadership Practices; *TL: Trust in Leaders

Table 15 shows that ethical leadership practices had a strong positive correlation ($r=0.659$) with the trust in leaders as professed by the public-school educators of Lahore, at high school level in Pakistan.

Correlation was calculated by using spearman's rank difference correlation on SPSS as the data was not normally distributed. This degree of association demonstrates that the leadership's reasonable and equitable actions are the only way to create trust in leadership.

The p value is 0.000 which is less than 0.05 which shows that there is a highly significant relationship amongst ELP and TL. Therefore, the null hypothesis is overruled, and alternate hypothesis is retained.

Comparison between the Three Groups

Table 16: Ranks

	Factor	N	Mean Rank
EL	Elementary	50	70.19
	Middle	50	67.59
	Higher Secondary	50	88.72
	Total	150	

Table 17

Test Statistics ^{a,b}			
		EL	
Chi-square		7.051	
Df		2	
Asymp. Sig.		.029	
a. Kruskal Wallis Test			
b. Grouping Variable: Factor			
Ranks			
	Factor	N	Mean Rank
EL	Elementary	50	70.19
	Middle	50	67.59
	Higher Secondary	50	88.72
	Total	150	
PC	Elementary	50	53.73
	Middle	50	52.08
	Higher Secondary	49	120.09
	Total	149	
TL	Elementary	50	63.43
	Middle	50	74.79
	Higher Secondary	50	88.28
	Total	150	
Test Statistics ^{a,b}			
	EL	PC	TL
Chi-square	7.051	80.042	8.245
Df	2	2	2
Asymp. Sig.	.029	.000	.016
a. Kruskal Wallis Test			
b. Grouping Variable: Factor			

Kruskal Wallis test which is a non-parametric test was used to match the median scores of the three groups and the results indicate the significant difference among these three groups. Elementary school group has been compared with the middle and high school groups and the results are significant. The difference between the elementary and middle school group, elementary and higher school group and middle and higher school group is significant for all the three variables i.e. ethical leadership practices, positive school climate and trust in leadership as alleged by the public school instructors of Lahore, Pakistan.

DISCUSSION

This study looked at how teachers in Lahore's public schools perceived the principal's management style, the school environment, and their own level of trust in him or her. The discussion here compares these perceptions to those from earlier studies that had similar outcomes and came to similar or otherwise conclusions.

The findings of some previous studies on school climate and trust in leaders are strikingly similar to those of this study. According to Copeland (2014), value-based leaders' actions are founded on moral and ethical principles, they are people-oriented, and they prioritise showing moral consideration for their workforce. According to O'Toole (2008), value-based headship emphasizes on upholding core principles that serve as a leader's moral compass. This, in turn, has a profound effect on followers' beliefs, needs, objectives, and work commitments. A morally driven person makes wise decisions based on ethics in any pressing scenario, according to Gurusamy and Thambu (2018).

Additionally, as principals is continuously dealing with problems of treachery, injustice, making choices, and enablement, moral leadership contributes to the development of a climate that is favourable to efficient schooling and teaching methods and the growth of trust (Copeland, 2014). Since core values serve as selfless guiding principles that assist members in acting and behaving when faced with difficult decision-making situations, value-based leaders who are motivated by moral principles have placed a strong emphasis on using them. The outcomes are in line with the results of numerous research studies. Roksa and Sawicka (2021) discovered that ethical leadership was positively associated with a positive school environment in a study conducted in Poland. This relationship was also found to be mediated by trust in leaders and teacher job satisfaction, rendering by the study. Another study held in Pakistan by Sabir et al., (2020) revealed that ethical leadership is positively associated with a positive school climate. The study also exposed that ethical governance was positively connected to teacher job gratification and school pledge.

Kim et al., (2021) asserted that ethical leadership was positively linked with a positive school climate, and that this relationship was intervened by teacher job satisfaction and trust in leaders in their study. Similarly, Huang et al., (2020) carried out a study in Taiwan. They discovered that trust in leaders and teacher empowerment facilitated the association between ethical management and a positive school environment.

A number of aspects of ethical leadership practices, a positive school environment, and trust in leaders, all have a noteworthy effect on the quality of education in public schools. This study set out to investigate how these elements interacted as seen by the Lahore public school instructors. The goal of the research was to deliver information on how ethical headship practises, a good school climate, and trust in leaders might enhance teacher's performance. An important area of educational research right now is how ethical leadership can foster a positive school atmosphere.

First research question in this study investigated by what means Lahore public school teachers of different levels perceived the relationship between an ethical principles headship style and development of a supportive learning environment. The study's findings shown a very strong link between moral leadership behaviour and the emergence of a supportive school environment that improves and maintains children's learning environments. The study also discovered that ethical leadership practices can increase teachers' trust in their leaders.

The study discovered consistent and strong association between principal's actions and the development of positive school climate at primary and high school's educational levels whereas at middle school level it was weak correlation and it was not highly significant. The study discovered that principals who effort to minimise struggles and uphold a tight-knit organization, give educators the freedom to take initiative and make their own choices, and perform with consideration for the comfort, betterment, and worth of staff contributions are more likely to foster a positive and constructive school atmosphere. Therefore, null hypotheses are rejected and alternate hypotheses are accepted at primary and high schools level.

Second question of this research study investigated the association amongst a principal's ethical governance practices and the level of trust alleged by Lahore's public-school teachers. The study discovered a strong and positive relationship amongst a principal's ethical leadership practices and the level of trust alleged by teachers at all stages of education, from elementary to high school.

According to the findings, ethical leadership behaviours such as respecting teachers' opinions and ideas, being transparent and honest in communication, and acting in the best interests of staff and students are critical factors in building trust with teachers. These actions instil confidence and security in teachers while also fostering a positive school culture in which everyone feels valued and respected.

CONCLUSION

The position of school head in the age of the Fourth Industrial Revolution is different than that of the ancient times, where the development of human resources and the concentration on technology-based resources require equal attention for the best possible organizational performance. An excellent principal will be adept at juggling the leadership and management responsibilities for the greatest outcomes in school performance as well as for "favourably encouraging." people forwarding towards more professional outlook and significant managerial actions (Mansor & Baki, 2007; Rizvi, 2008). The current study found that ethical headship which is regarded as Leadership grounded in values style is the main determinant of positive school climate for the student's durable learning and building trust in leadership. The study has been carried out from the perspective of public-school teachers of Lahore district in 2022 – 2023. The findings involving the perception of 150 teachers from three levels (primary, middle and high school) show that the value-based leadership (ethical leadership practices) is an integral part of our educational system, without this, long term aims and objectives cannot be reached so far. But along

with this, the staff and teacher's morale and honesty cannot be ignored. The study looks closely at relationships, positive school learning climate, and trust in leaders within the framework of schools. The findings revealed statistically significant differences in perceptions of ethical leadership, positive school climate and trust in leadership across three groups of schools i.e elementary, middle and high school. Future initiatives involving principals and educators will be more capable to make extensive use of the data to enhance already effective training materials, outlines, and simulations that emphasize ethical leadership or foster trust for an educational workforce, that is highly goal-driven, long-lasting, and constantly growing.

As this study was limited to public schools, in future it can be extended to the private sector as well. According to the study, ethical leadership is a strong complement and should be integrated into other types of headship, as instructive, transformative, and technological leadership. The results motivate more research on the influence of ethical leadership among higher education managers. "Integrating ethical leadership principles can aid administrators in balancing their many tasks, which in turn can help teachers."

The ethical leadership style of administrators is expected to foster a moral and trustworthy workplace culture that is suitable for encouraging teachers to engage in productive work behaviours. It is probable to increase coach effectiveness along with their creativeness and originality (Yidong & Xinxin, 2013). Findings of the present study are consistent with the suggestions for forthcoming research emphasizing the advantages of ethical leadership perspective in the setting of advanced education institutions.

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